

Assessment of knowledge, attitudes, and practices of healthcare providers on pharmacovigilance: a cross-sectional survey in general hospitals in Iraq

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Received 5 June 2025 ♦ Accepted 11 August 2025 ♦ Published 1 September 2025

Citation: Saleem AH, Al-Qazaz HKh, Allela OQ (2025) Assessment of knowledge, attitudes, and practices of healthcare providers on pharmacovigilance: a cross-sectional survey in general hospitals in Iraq. *Pharmacia* 72: 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e161134>

Abstract

Background: Pharmacovigilance's main goal is to improve patient outcomes. This study aimed to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of healthcare providers (HCPs) regarding pharmacovigilance and adverse drug reaction (ADR) reporting in general hospitals in Nineveh.

Materials and methods: A cross-sectional survey was conducted among HCPs in general hospitals of Mosul City. It consisted of four sections (demographic data, and questions related to knowledge, attitudes, and practices).

Results: A total of 391 HCPs took part in this study. Of them, 242 were aware of the purpose of pharmacovigilance; however, only 167 defined it correctly. Only 126 HCPs reported ADRs, although 329 HCPs stated that they are willing to implement ADR reporting practices. Profession played a critical role in determining both knowledge and practice scores, where pharmacists exhibited the highest scores ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: The findings of this study highlight the insufficient knowledge among HCPs along with significant underreporting.

Keywords

adverse drug reaction, drug safety, underreporting

Introduction

In 1972, the World Health Organization (WHO 1972) defined an adverse drug reaction (ADR) as “a response to a drug that is noxious and unintended and occurs at doses normally used in humans for the prophylaxis, diagnosis, or therapy of disease, or for modification of

physiological function.” Before being launched onto the market, the efficacy and safety of medications must be assessed, evaluated, and confirmed (Gupta and Udupa 2011). Still, when the medications are made available for the general populace, ADRs that were not identified during the carefully controlled setting of the clinical trials may appear (Banat et al. 2022).

ADRs are considered a major health problem throughout the world, leading to economic and health-related issues and even death (Formica et al. 2018). ADRs are considered the cause of hospitalization in about 0.3%–11% of hospital admissions, whereas 10% of hospital stays are extended due to ADRs (Bouvy et al. 2015). Although ADRs have a preventable nature, they are still regarded as one of the top ten leading causes of death in many countries (WHO 2004b). Consistently, a meta-analysis from the United States reported that ADRs are the fifth most common cause of death in that country (Lazarou et al. 1998). Close monitoring facilitates the early detection of ADRs, and this practice is essential to safeguard patients from harm, to reduce the costs of healthcare services, to maximize drug safety, and to guide regulatory decisions (Al Rabayah and Al Rumman 2019).

Pharmacovigilance (PV) is defined as “the science and activities relating to the detection, assessment, understanding, and prevention of adverse effects or any other drug-related problems” (WHO 2002). Its main goals are to improve patient outcomes related to drug use, to assess the benefits, risks, harms, and effectiveness of medications, and to deliver medication safety information to both healthcare providers (HCPs) and the public (WHO 2004a). PV plays a key role in minimizing ADRs, so continued advancement in this science is essential to deliver effective clinical care (Albayrak and Karahalil 2022). ADR reporting is the backbone of PV, as it provides essential data for identifying and addressing potential risks (Elkhwsky et al. 2021).

HCPs play a central role in achieving a solid PV system, as patients usually do not tend to contact pharmaceutical companies to report ADRs; rather, they inform their pharmacists, physicians, or other HCPs (Albayrak and Karahalil 2022). The contribution of HCPs to ADR reporting is crucial to ensure the safety of medications; they must be able to detect ADRs early, to document their details, and to report them to the appropriate authorities (Gonzalez-Gonzalez et al. 2013). An effective PV system relies mainly on the contributions of HCPs in reporting ADRs and effective communication between HCPs and national PV centers (Almandil 2016).

Although underreporting of ADRs is a global concern, it is especially widespread in developing countries (Suyagh et al. 2015). Iraq has gone through many conflicts over decades, and Mosul City specifically was affected by the Islamic State of Iraq and Syria (ISIS) offense in 2016, which led to the destruction of 70% of the city’s hospitals and hindered advancement in the health sector for many years (M’Aiber et al. 2022). Several studies have demonstrated a correlation between insufficient PV knowledge, attitudes, and practices among HCPs and ADR underreporting (Danekhu et al. 2021; Khan et al. 2022; Hayek et al. 2024). So, it is necessary to understand the baseline knowledge, attitudes, and practices of HCPs to develop an effective strategy to encourage reporting (Alharbi et al. 2016). In addition, this information can be used to strengthen the existing PV system through highlighting the main gaps

(Shamim et al. 2016; Adisa et al. 2019). Up to now, only a few PV studies have been performed in Nineveh (Al-Mukhtar et al. 2024; Younus et al. 2025). However, these studies did not investigate the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of HCPs. Hence, we aimed to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of HCPs—physicians, pharmacists, and nurses—regarding PV and ADR reporting in general hospitals in Nineveh.

Materials and methods

Study design, setting, and population

A cross-sectional, self-administered, face-to-face, questionnaire-based survey was conducted in Mosul City, Iraq. This study sampled the HCPs working in three general hospitals in Mosul City, namely Al-Salam Teaching Hospital, Al-Mosul General Hospital, and Ibn Sina Teaching Hospital. The data were collected between November 2024 and April 2025. Physicians, pharmacists, and nurses were the professions sampled. HCPs working at the PV centers in hospitals and healthcare students were excluded.

Sample size and sampling technique

The registered total number of physicians, pharmacists, and nurses working at the three general hospitals in Mosul is about 2000. Using the Raosoft online software sample size calculator, the minimum required sample size was 377 with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. However, the target size was increased to 400 to account for any missing data. All physicians, pharmacists, and nurses working at the three previously mentioned general hospitals were invited to participate.

Questionnaire development

Previous papers that evaluated the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of HCPs were reviewed to generate questions for the questionnaire used in the present study (Gupta et al. 2015; Alsaleh et al. 2017; Farha et al. 2018; Tahir and Hussein 2020; Abdulsalim et al. 2023; El-Dahiyat et al. 2023; Shenoy et al. 2023; Salih et al. 2024). However, they were culturally adapted and aligned with the aim of this study and community standards. After that, the questionnaire was translated according to the guidelines recommended by (Beaton et al. 2000). Four translators were involved in forward and backward translation. The translated versions were reviewed by the author team, and then the final Arabic version of the questionnaire was made available for validation. A pilot study was conducted to test the comprehensibility of the questionnaire to ensure that it accurately measures the required objectives (Saleem et al. 2025/06/04). It included 30 HCPs—10 physicians, 10 pharmacists, and 10 nurses—who were excluded from our study sample. The instrument showed both strong face content and

construct validity; these parameters were examined by experts in the subject matter. The reliability of the questionnaire was within the acceptable range; that is, Cronbach's alpha was > 0.7 (specifically 0.729 for knowledge, 0.722 for attitude, and 0.722 for practice).

Data collection instrument

The final Arabic version of the questionnaire consisted of four sections: The first section collected the demographic data of the participant, including name, age, gender, profession, education level, and years of practice. The second section included 14 multiple-choice questions that assessed the knowledge of HCPs of PV and ADR reporting. The third section included six questions that investigated the attitudes of HCPs toward ADR reporting; they were rated on a Likert scale. The fourth section included six questions (close-ended and multiple choice) that assessed the HCP's practices of ADRs reporting, investigated the history of previous ADRs reporting training, and determined the possible causes for underreporting according to HCPs opinions.

Statistical analysis

After coding the collected data, analysis was conducted using SPSS Statistics version 25. The median, interquartile range (25th and 75th percentiles), frequency, percentage, and range (minimum and maximum) were calculated. In addition, univariate analysis was conducted using the Mann–Whitney U test, the Kruskal–Wallis tests were performed, and Spearman correlation coefficients were calculated.

Ethical approval

The Ethical Committee of the Health Directorate of Nineveh approved this study (meeting number: 261, research number: 2024210, date: 6th of November 2024). Each participant provided verbal consent before filling out the questionnaire. They were assured that their information and responses would remain confidential.

Results

Demographic data

Table 1 provides the demographic data of our participants. The response rate was 97.75% (391 out of 400 participants). Most respondents were females (60.9%). The median (interquartile range) age was 28 (25–32) years, and the median (interquartile range) experience was 2 (1–6) years, ranging from 1 year to 36 years. Bachelor's degree holders made up the majority of our sample (90%), while master's and PhD degree holders represented 4.3% and 5.6% of the sample, respectively. Among the three hospitals, 47.3% worked at Al-Salam Teaching Hospital, 24.6% worked at Al-Mosul General Hospital, and 28.1% worked at Ibn Sina Teaching Hospital. Nurses comprised 41.7% of the participants, followed by pharmacists (38.6%) and physicians (19.7%).

Table 1. Demographic data of the study participants (n = 391).

Parameter	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	153	39.1
	Female	238	60.9
Profession	Physician	77	19.7
	Pharmacist	151	38.6
	Nurse	163	41.7
Education level	Bachelor's degree	352	90.0
	Master's degree	17	4.3
	PhD degree	22	5.6
Place of work	Al-Salam Teaching Hospital	185	47.3
	Al-Mosul General Hospital	96	24.6
	Ibn Sina Teaching Hospital	110	28.1

Knowledge of PV and ADR reporting

Overall, 61.9% of the participants claimed they were aware of the purpose of PV; however, only 42.7% knew the correct definition of PV. We found that 65% of the participants understood the concept of ADRs and 32.5% were familiar with the establishment of Iraq's national PV center. However, 26.6% of the participants were unaware of any medications that had been globally banned due to ADRs (Table 2).

Table 2. Knowledge of pharmacovigilance and adverse drug reaction reporting among the study participants (n = 391).

Knowledge parameters	Frequency (%) of the correct answer
K1. Pharmacovigilance is	167 (42.7)
K2. The purpose of pharmacovigilance is	242 (61.9)
K3. Medicine had been banned due to an adverse drug reaction	287 (73.4)
K4. Adverse drug reaction is	254 (65.0)
K5. Adverse drug reactions that should be reported are	306 (78.3)
K6. All suspected adverse drug reactions associated with drug-food interactions should be reported	327 (83.6)
K7. Adverse drug reactions should be reported only if they are of a serious nature	202 (51.7)
K8. Adverse drug reactions should not be reported until the specific medication that caused them is known	123 (31.5)
K9. Adverse drug reactions can be identified during this phase of clinical trials	39 (10.0)
K10. The pharmacovigilance center of Iraq was officially established in the year of	127 (32.5)
K11. The international center for adverse drug reaction monitoring is located in	87 (22.3)
K12. A serious adverse event in Iraq should be reported to the regulatory within	28 (7.2)
K13. The healthcare professional(s) responsible for reporting adverse drug reactions in a hospital is/are	250 (63.9)
K14. The information required for an adverse drug reaction case report is	305 (78.0)

Attitudes of HCPs

Table 3 summarizes the attitudes of the participants. The vast majority of the participants (96.9%) believed that ADR reporting is necessary, and 96.6% thought that ADR reporting is a professional obligation. Moreover, 92.1% of the participants stated that HCPs should be provided with educational ADR reporting workshops. In addition, 84.1% of the participants indicated that they would be willing to implement ADR reporting during their practice. Of note, 80.9% of the participants agreed that there is a lack of awareness regarding the process of reporting. Finally, 77.7% of the participants thought that ADRs increase the cost for healthcare.

Table 3. Attitudes toward adverse drug reaction reporting among the study participants (n = 391), presented as the frequency (percentage).

Attitude parameter	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
A1. Reporting of adverse drug reactions is necessary	273 (69.8)	106 (27.1)	7 (1.8)	3 (0.8)	2 (0.5)
A2. Adverse drug reaction reporting is a professional obligation	257 (65.7)	121 (30.9)	10 (2.6)	2 (0.5)	1 (0.3)
A3. Pharmacovigilance should be taught in detail to healthcare professionals	202 (51.7)	158 (40.4)	24 (6.1)	7 (1.8)	0 (0)
A4. You are willing to implement adverse drug reaction reporting in your practice	124 (31.7)	205 (52.4)	42 (10.7)	18 (4.6)	2 (0.5)
A5. There is a lack of information and awareness of the adverse drug reaction reporting process	107 (27.4)	209 (53.5)	53 (13.6)	16 (4.1)	6 (1.5)
A6. Adverse drug reactions increase the healthcare cost in your facility	99 (25.3)	205 (52.4)	51 (13)	27 (6.9)	9 (2.3)

Practices of HCPs

As shown in Table 4, 62.9% of the participants had identified ADRs during their practice, but only 32.2% of them had reported ADRs. Moreover, only 35.5% of the participants had received ADR reporting training.

Barriers to ADR reporting

According to the participants, the major barrier hindering ADR reporting is a lack of information from patients (39.1%), followed by inadequate promotion by authorities (24.0%), and not knowing how and where to report (20.7%). Time constraints were reported less frequently by the participants (12.0%), indicating that knowledge-related issues are the primary challenges (Table 5).

Knowledge, attitude, and practice differences among groups of HCPs

Table 6 shows several differences in the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of the study participants—divided by education level, gender, and profession—toward PV and ADR reporting. For gender, the knowledge score did not differ between males and females; males had a slightly higher but nonsignificant attitude score compared with females ($p = 0.297$); and females had a significantly higher practice score ($p = 0.007$). There were notable differences in the knowledge and practice scores among the professions: the pharmacists had higher scores compared with the physicians and nurses. Despite the fact we assessed positive correlations of age and experience to knowledge, practice, and attitude, the strength of these correlations was very weak (Table 7).

Discussion

The concept of PV relies mainly on two critical components—the early identification and timely reporting of ADRs—as they play a pivotal role in ensuring patient safety and enhancing therapeutic outcomes. Undetected ADRs may lead to serious consequences, including prolonged hospitalization, treatment failure, and sometimes even death. ADR reporting enables regulatory authorities to detect safety signals, update treatment guidelines, and implement risk minimization strategies. Therefore, empowering HCPs to actively engage in ADR reporting is essential to strengthen PV systems, provide safer clinical practice, and protect public health.

Table 4. Practices toward adverse drug reaction identification and reporting among the study participants (n = 391).

Practice parameters	Frequency (%) of the correct practice
Adverse drug reaction identification	246 (62.9)
Availability of reporting forms	216 (55.2)
Adverse drug reaction reporting	126 (32.2)
Number of adverse drug reactions reported	
<5	83 (21.2)
5–10	29 (7.4)
>10	16 (4.1)
Previous pharmacovigilance training	139 (35.5)

Table 5. Barriers to adverse drug reaction reporting according to the study participants (n = 391).

Barriers	Frequency	Percentage
Lack of information provided by patients	153	39.1
I don't have enough time	47	12.0
I am not sure how and where to report	81	20.7
The appropriate authorities do not actively promote it	94	24.0
Others	16	4.1

We conducted a questionnaire-based survey to evaluate the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of HCPs toward ADR reporting in the three general hospitals of Mosul. The response rate was 97.75%, which is comparable to the rate reported in other studies (Almandil 2016; Al Rabayah and Al Rumman 2019; Shanableh et al. 2023; Shareef et al. 2024). The HCPs showed low overall knowledge of PV. Although 61.9% of our participants claimed that they were aware of the purpose of PV, only 42.7% were able to choose its

Table 6. Differences in knowledge, attitude, and practice by gender, education, and profession.

Variable	Education level	Profession	Gender
Number (%)	Bachelor's: 352 (90.0%) Master's: 17 (4.3%) PhD: 22 (5.6%)	Physicians: 77 (19.7%) Pharmacist: 151 (38.6%) Nurses: 163 (41.7%)	Males: 153 (39.1%) Females: 238 (60.9%)
Knowledge score	7.0 (6–9)	7.0 (6–9)	7.0 (5–8)
Median (interquartile range)	8.0 (5–8)	8.0 (7–10)	7.0 (6–9)
	8.0 (7–10)	6.0 (4–7)	
P-value	0.112	<0.001*	0.456
Attitude score	26.0 (24–27)	27.0 (25–28)	26.0 (24–28)
Median (interquartile range)	27.0 (24–28)	26.0 (24–28)	26.0 (24–27)
	27.0 (25–29)	26.0 (24–27)	
P-value	0.286	0.069	0.297
Practice score	2.0 (1–4)	1.0 (1–2)	1.0 (1–3)
Median (interquartile range)	3.0 (1–6)	3.0 (2–5)	2.0 (1–5)
	1.0 (1–3)	1.0 (1–3)	
P-value	0.218	<0.001*	0.007*

*p-value is significant.

Table 7. Correlations between the age and years of professional experience with the knowledge, practice, and attitude scores.

Variable	Knowledge, rho (p-value)	Attitude, rho (p-value)	Practice, rho (p-value)
Age	0.194 (<0.001*)	0.134 (0.008*)	0.160 (0.001*)
Years of practice	0.145 (0.004*)	0.063 (0.008*)	0.182 (<0.001*)

*p-value is significant.

correct definition, which is consistent with another study (42.64%) conducted in Egyptian hospitals (Tolba et al. 2022). We found that 73.4% of our participants knew that medications had been banned due to causing ADRs. Also, 65.0% of our participants were able to define the ADR concept, and 78.3% were aware of the types of ADRs that should be reported, similar to the results obtained in another study conducted in Saudi Arabia (Almandil 2016). However, 68.5% of our participants thought that ADRs should not be reported until the medication causing them has been identified. In addition, only 32.5% of the participants were familiar with the establishment of the Iraqi Pharmacovigilance Center, and 22.3% knew that the international ADR reporting center is based in Sweden; these findings are consistent with a cross-sectional study performed in Aden, Yemen (Alshakka et al. 2015). Finally, the majority of our participants (92.8%) were unaware of the time window for reporting ADRs. Similarly, HCPs in Alexandria were unaware of the ADR reporting time frame (Elkhwsky et al. 2021).

Concerning attitudes, 96.9% of the participants strongly agreed or agreed that ADR reporting is necessary, therefore demonstrating positive attitudes. A study from Saudi Arabia demonstrated similar results, where 97.0% of the sample agreed on the necessity of ADR reporting and its role in enhancing medication safety (Alshabi et al. 2022). Among our participants, 96.6% believed that ADR reporting is part of their professional obligations. However, there were very different results in a similar study, where only 39% of the participants agreed that reporting is their responsibility (Alqahtani et al. 2023).

The majority of our participants (92.1%) believed that PV should be taught to HCPs, which is consistent

with the percentage (80.4%) reported by (Al Rabayah and Al Rumman 2019) in their investigation of the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of HCPs in a cancer center in Jordan. We found that 84.1% of our participants would be willing to implement ADR reporting in their practice. However, 80.9% believed that there is a lack of information and awareness of the process of ADR reporting, which indicates a gap between the willingness of HCPs to report ADRs and their practical knowledge to implement reporting. Finally, 77.7% of our participants believed that ADRs increase the cost of healthcare services, a finding that reflects their awareness of the economic impact of ADRs. Overall, while the attitude toward ADR reporting is positive, there is an evident need for more education and support to enable effective implementation. Educating HCPs on PV will reinforce positive attitudes and lead to a feasible increment in ADR reporting rates.

The majority of our participants (62.9%) have encountered and identified ADRs through the course of their clinical practice, and 55.2% stated that reporting forms are available at their unit. However, only 32.2% of them have successfully reported these ADRs to the PV center, thus exhibiting poor practices toward ADR reporting. This poor practice has also been highlighted by other studies in Qatar (29.3%) (Wilbur 2013), Saudi Arabia (32.1%) (Alshayban et al. 2020), and Pakistan (32.4%) (Hussain et al. 2021). These results emphasize the gap between the identification and reporting of ADRs. A very small percentage of our sample (4.1%) had reported more than 10 ADRs, about 7.4% had reported 5–10 ADRs, and 21.2% had reported < 5 ADRs during their practice. Only 35.5% of our participants had received training regarding ADR reporting.

This is comparable to the percentages reported in other studies (35.2% and 41.6%) (Al-Hazmi and Naylor 2013; Alqahtani et al. 2023).

According to our participants, the most common barriers hindering ADR reporting are a lack of information provided by patients, PV and ADRs not actively being promoted by the authorities, not being sure about how or where to report, and not having enough time. Other studies identified the same factors contributing to underreporting, in addition to lack of reporting forms and fear of legal issues (Adegbuyi et al. 2021; Khan et al. 2023; Rijims 2023).

Profession played a critical role in determining both knowledge and practice scores. The pharmacists in our study had higher knowledge and practice scores ($p < 0.001$), a finding similar to a study in Qatar (Rijims 2023). In addition, active engagement in PV activities is clearly linked to the professional maturity of HCPs: the knowledge and practice scores showed positive correlations with age and professional experience. This finding might be due to the fact that older HCPs with more experience have been exposed to a high number of ADRs during their practice. As a result, they are more used to the reporting protocols and more confident in implementing reporting practices. However, there were contrasting results in a study conducted in Saudi Arabia, where knowledge and practice scores showed no correlation with the age or professional experience of HCPs (Abdulsalim et al. 2023). Female HCPs exhibited statistically significantly higher practice scores compared with male HCPs. However, (Al Rabayah and Al Rumman 2019) found that in Jordan, males have significantly higher practice scores than females.

Improving ADR reporting requires a comprehensive approach that includes educational and supportive policies. Moreover, academic institutions should collaborate with health authorities to develop targeted training programs tailored to healthcare settings, supported by clear guidelines and regulations, along with the implementation of the PV concept and ADR reporting in the undergraduate curriculums. Enhancing communication across all levels of the healthcare system can further strengthen PV efforts. Additionally, health authorities play a pivotal role through organizing educational lectures, organizing practical training sessions, and creating a workplace environment where HCPs are motivated to report ADRs accurately and consistently.

Strengths and limitations

The strength of our study is that it is the first, to our knowledge, that has evaluated the knowledge, attitudes, and practices toward PV and ADR reporting among HCPs in Mosul City, Iraq. However, our study has some limitations. First, we only included HCPs who work at governmental hospitals. Therefore, our results cannot be extrapolated to HCPs working at private healthcare centers and hospitals. Second, we conducted our study in Mosul City, so the

results cannot be generalized to the entire governorate of Nineveh. Finally, we used a cross-sectional design, so our study could not prove causality.

Conclusion

The findings of our study highlight the insufficient knowledge among HCPs along with significant underreporting regardless of the positive attitudes exhibited towards ADR reporting. The male participants in this study showed a lower practice score compared with the female participants. The pharmacists showed significantly higher knowledge and practice scores compared with the nurses and physicians. The knowledge and practice scores were significantly higher among older HCPs with more experience. A specifically tailored strategy can greatly enhance the knowledge-practice gaps and thereby ensure patient safety. The collected data will be employed to create a customized intervention that aims to improve the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of HCPs in Mosul. Further research should be carried out to investigate the impact of this intervention on the KAP of HCPs.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Directorate of Health in Nineveh

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

No funding was reported.

Author contributions

All authors have made substantial contributions to the conception of the study, drafting the article, and final approval of the version to be submitted. AH and HKh conceived and designed the study. AH did the electronic search for the relevant articles and drafted the manuscript. OQ analyzed the data. OQ and HKh revised and edited the manuscript. AH, OQ, and HKh prepared the manuscript for publication. All authors have read and approved the final submitted manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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